

THE WORKS OF HIS HOLINESS MIR ALISHER NAVOI - A TREASURE OF ETERNITY

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Hazrat Navoi is one of the unique individuals who left an indelible mark on the history of mankind. He is a great scholar who mastered the Qur'an, Hadith, Tafsir, Fiqh, Sufism, poetry, literature, linguistics, philosophy, and other sciences. Allomani's works belong to eternity and are the treasure of the peoples of the world. That is why the national poet of Uzbekistan, Abdulla Oripov, while evaluating His Holiness Navoi, says, "Alisher took the place where Timur's blade did not touch, with a pen."

The work "Khamsa" consisting of 25,615 stanzas, which is considered the peak of Alisher Navoi's work, consists of five epics and is considered the first work in the Turkish language created in this genre. Allama has proved that it is possible to create a work on the same level as Persian-Tajik literature in the Chigatoi language (old Uzbek language) through these five treasures. This work is a great literary monument that covers almost all social issues characteristic of this period, and at the same time, it expresses the great ability and high power of the poet.

Alisher Navoi divides his entire lyrical heritage written in Uzbek language into four divans according to the four seasons of his life. The first one is "Garoyibus sig'ar" ("The wonders of childhood"), the second one is "Navodirush shabab" ("Rarities of youth"), the third one is "Badoyiul wasat" ("The beauties of middle age") and the last one is "Favoyidul kibar" ("The benefits of old age").

gives the name This collection of four divans is called "Khazayinul maoniy" ("Treasury of Meanings").

Looking back at history, we can see that until the 15th century, people looked down on the Turkish language and said, "This language is the language of the common people, it is impossible to create using it." But Mir Alisher Navoi, the sultan of the ghazal estate, created "Khamsa" for the first time in the world, i.e. five epics and other large, artistically perfect works, and brought this language out of the mire of enmity into the sky of justice. Alisher Navoi is the most mature writer of Eastern literature both in terms of quantity and quality. Alloma writes in his epic "Lisonut-tyre":

Turk nazmida chu men tortib kalam,
Ayladim ul mamlakatni yakkalam... [1]

(Meaning: I raised the banner of Turkish poetry and united all Turkish speakers under one literary language).

From the poems written by Hazrat Navoi in the Persian language, a separate book called "Book of Foni" is organized. It contains 554 ghazals, 1 musaddas, 1 march, 72 verses, 73 rubai, 16 histories, 373 problems, 9 lugz (poetic riddles) - a total of 1131 poems, which consists of 6197 verses.

In the works of the famous thinker, obedience to the Creator, glorification of man and care for him, love for humanity, motherland, devotion to knowledge, love of nature, the taste of life, the pleasure of love, the pain of emigration, the hope of future generations, complaints about the times, resentment against evil, the high quality inherent in man, motifs such as noble human pride and human humility and deep philosophical themes are sung with great skill.

According to Alisher Navoi, love for the Motherland begins with love for the people living in this country. The great scholar puts forward the idea that a person is the dearest, most valuable, most honorable, most holy, and most beautiful both in the outer and inner world of the entire universe. Navoi interprets love into two

aspects, i.e., divine love and metaphorical love, and he does not consider figurative love to be inferior to divine love, which consists of kindness, respect, and loyalty to people.

To a real person who has high human qualities, - says Navoi, - the marks come and worship:

Odamiyliq ko'rguzub qilding parivashlarni qul,

Odam uldurkim, maloyik oni masjid ayladi [2].

According to Hazrat Navoi, science helps a person to overcome life's difficulties and worries, that's why he says, "If you want to leave the world without worries, you have learned a skill." If you have knowledge and skills, if you apply honesty and integrity to them, you will always be successful, and you will reach your goal, he says.

"If the work of the world is enmity with the people, the scholar will be despised, and the ignorant will be honored. As long as the world does not abandon tyranny, the tree will grow tall and the fruit will fall to the ground. High ranks will be for the poor, suffering for the learned, stones will be on top of the mountain, and wealth and mines will be under it. Allama believes that those who have bad deeds occupy high positions and subjugate the world. That's why our Grandfather Navoi says that the world should only serve the people, all forms of tyranny should be rejected, only then will the talent show itself, the scholar and virtue will be respected, and there will be no place for the ignorant in the society.

Alisher Navoi, who cared for his people all his life, put the interests of the people above his personal experiences. He wrote in one of his ghazals: "If I suffer a hundred hardships, I will cry once, but if the people are oppressed once, I will cry a hundred times", which shows how true and noble his humanity is.

Navoi understands the thing that separates man from animals, that is, language, as a sacred gem, therefore, when speaking, a person should think and speak briefly and meaningfully, not the words that come to his mouth, and the

listener should also keep this goal in mind, giving importance to "not who is saying, but what is being said." must hear:

Chun g'araz so'zdin erur ma'ni ango,

Noqil o'lsa xoh xotun, xoh er.

So'zchi holin boqma, boq so'z holini,

Ko'rma kim der, oni ko'rgil – kim ne der [4].

Then, - says Navoi, - keep the precious words you hear in your ear, appreciate them, if there is no dur in the Sadaf, will it have any value?

Alisher Navoi believed that the whole universe is a mirror of the Supreme Truth and that the universe was established due to God's grace and mercy, and he knew that the destruction of the universe shows God's wrath.

It is known that during the time of the former union, any ideology in society was denied, people's minds were subordinated to communist ideology, and fiction, among other things, fell into the trap of the policy of alienation and secularization. Our classical literature before the "revolution" was sharply criticized, and socialist literature was established instead. This literature was an ideological "idea" aimed at the policy of razing one's nation to the ground and consecrating the communist party. This literature, which called itself the literature of socialist realism, did not hesitate to distort the reality of life in favor of communism. Even Alisher, who has left an indelible mark in world literature, interprets Navoi as a person who indulges in various limitations wrongly idealizes God, and accuses him of not understanding the laws of nature. They explain this by the period in which the sultan of the ghazal estate lived and the level of the concepts of this period. They say that at that time, nonsense about heaven and hell, and fiction about the torments of hell were absorbed into the people's consciousness. These fabrications cause mental pain to the people and create a mood of hopelessness and depression in them. Alisher Navoi began to lose this mood and put forward the idea that a person disappears

after death, therefore, one should try to live a good life knowing the value of life, and he slanders our great-grandfather.

Alisher Navoiy artistically reflected the main philosophical and moral views of religion in his royal works and promoted them with excellent artistry. The well-known scientist Dilnavoz Yusupova stated that Alisher Navoi's work "Siroju-l-muslimin" ("Light of Muslims") has a purely religious direction and is dedicated to clarifying the rules of Islam. The work is written in the form of masnavi and consists of 197 verses. "Siroju-l-muslimin" includes praise and praise, the reason for writing the book, a review of jurisprudential and dogmatic issues related to Islam, and a conclusion. Hazrat Nawai, first of all, praises God and sends his blessings and greetings to our Prophet Muhammad, may God bless him and grant him peace, then he goes to the explanation of the reason for this poem [5].

The great thinker, while explaining how a believer should feel, writes:

Mo‘min emastur ulki, iymondin
Ro‘zgorida yuz safo ko‘rgay,
Toki qardoshig‘a ravo ko‘rmas –
Har nekim o‘ziga ravo ko‘rgay [6].

Unfortunately, even now, we do not understand Navoi, we do not always read his works and we do not listen to Purmana's advice. That's why some people, even some people who have occupied a high positions, are drowning in the mire of vices and sins, such as greed, theft, bribery, greed, lying, and gaining wealth, albeit by illegal means. Such people, along with betraying their people and homeland, are turning both their world and this world into darkness.

Alisher Navoi describes greed as the worst vice, and he says that whoever does not have this quality is a person worthy of honor. Another of the bad qualities condemned by the great thinker is serving others and speaking flattering words. Navoi considers the owner of such qualities worthy of any punishment:

Kimki maxluq xizmatig‘a kamar

Chust etar – yaxshiroq ushalsa beli.

Qo‘l qovushturg‘uncha bu avlodur

Ki, aning chiqsa egni, sinsa ali.

Chun xushomad demakni boshlasa kosh

Kim, tutulsa dami, kesilsa tili [7].

(Content: it is better to break one's back if one ties a belt to the service of a creature. It is better to lose one's neck and break one's hand than to stand in front of that creature. If one starts flattering that creature, what if his breath returns and his tongue is cut off).

Navoi also criticizes qualities such as avarice, lying, and laziness, praising generosity, solidarity, honesty, and hard work.

People who run away from wealth and look at the world with greed, says Navoi, - become slaves of this world, a person who gets rich by eating someone else's rights, worries about his wealth day and night, loses his happiness, and even becomes ruined. Navoi wrote in one of his ghazals that the wealth accumulated through greed is a disease that accumulates in a person's organs. The poet says, "Don't reach for gold, your hand will be black, if you keep your anger towards it in your heart, your heart will also be black."

Ko‘b oltun, kumush sori qo‘l sunmog‘in,

Ki tutsang kafingning qaro rang etar.

Ko‘ngulda dog‘i maylini asrama

Ki, ko‘nglungni dog‘i ham ul rang etar.

Navoi warns you not to be shackled by the chain of deceit, not to go close to devilish people, strongly condemns drunkenness, and looks with hatred at people who are given to hypocrisy, deceit, and hooliganism. If someone points out an existing defect or fault in you, don't get upset and interrupt him, otherwise he won't talk to you about it later. A poet can compare a person who shows guilt to a mirror-mirror.

Speaking in the chapter of doing good, Navoi states that this is a feeling characteristic of a real person, which adorns him. He considers it a noble thing to extend a helping hand to the poor and the downtrodden in particular:

Kimki, bir ko'ngli buzug'ning xotirin shod aylagay,
Oncha borkim, Ka'ba vayron bo'lsa, obod aylagay [8].

It is known that the Kaaba is the holiest place in the entire Muslim world, and circumambulating it is considered an extremely great merit. If someone does good to a poor person and lifts his spirits, he has done a great deed like beautifying the Kaaba, which is considered the holiest place, says the great poet.

Based on the moral requirements of the Naqshbandi order, Alisher Navoi considers a person who can keep up with his time and who always strives for perfection to be a moral example. "No one in Uzbek literature has sung the issues of human education and perfection as well as he did. The thinker-poet considers the essence of humanity to be in his social activity - engaging in a profession useful to society, benefiting the people, and alleviating people's burdens" [9]. Indeed, this is proved by the following verses of the poet:

Odami ersang demagil odami,
Onikim yo'q xalq g'amidin g'ami [10].

(Meaning: if you are a real person, do not consider the person who does not care about the people to be a perfect person).

So, as the Russian scientist Yevgeny Eduardovich Bertels said, "Studying Alisher Navoi's work is the task not only of the Uzbek people, but of all nations, because his great works are the property of the entire world culture." Navoi's work is a museum exhibit, not a piece of history. He lives and will continue to live" [11]. Indeed, understanding Hazrat Mir Alisher Navoi, the famous poet, the sultan of words, statesman, seeker of knowledge, science and education workers, patron of the needy and helpless, founder of many foundations, is one of the main tasks of today. Because the person who understands it, enjoys his works and follows the

instructions in them increases his level of perfection, becomes committed to serving his country and people, drinks water from the source of spirituality and enlightenment, avoids various vices, in a word, literally deserves to be called a human being.

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